

Multi-parametric, label-free and non-contact approach to bacteria single-cells and biofilm formation detection

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Abstract

Understanding the mechanism of biofilm formation is essential to progress in the field of microbiology and infection control. Here we demonstrate a new approach to detect bacterial single cell and biofilms using label-free and non-contact methods. Multimode measurements using Kelvin probe, digital holographic tomography and infrared microscopy were performed on *E. coli* cells. The proposed analysis provides the multi-parametric detection of bacteria based on contact potential difference, refractive index data and infrared spectra related to electrical, optical, morphological, and chemical properties of the single cells. Moreover, it is the first attempt to use the Kelvin Probe and contact potential difference measurements for bacteria sensing. The obtained results confirmed that it is possible to use the mentioned above techniques for examination of the biofilm formation. Furthermore, it was confirmed that after only 24 hours *E. coli* bacteria formed biofilm on the analyzed surfaces without the presence of any nutrients.

Keywords: Kelvin Probe, Contact Potential Difference, Digital Holographic Tomography, Infrared Microscopy, Bacteria, Single-Cells, Biofilm Formation

38

39 **Highlights**

40

41 • Multi-parametric label-free sensing of the biofilm formation on different
42 surfaces.

43 • Suitable method for transparent/ non-transparent, conducting/semi- or non-
44 conducting materials.

45 • Multi-mode large-scale examination by Kelvin probe, Holotomography and IR -
46 microscopy

47 • Contact Potential Difference measurement for detection of biofilm
48 development.

49 • Confirmation of biofilm formation on glass and stainless steel after 24 hours.

50

51 **1. INTRODUCTION**

52 The technological developments are omnipresent and becoming more and more
53 applied in our everyday life. The devices that historically have been used in particular
54 application became multifunctional products. The phones, which were used for verbal
55 communications, have advanced with the development of the wireless technology, and
56 apart from its primary function became our cameras, data storage, wallets, social life
57 centers and health monitors. Mobile solutions are revolutionizing the modern
58 medicine, as the collection, hosting and managing of relevant data became accessible,
59 easy, paper free and manageable.

60 The advancement in remote medicine has made a substantial impact during
61 the world-wide Covid-19 pandemic. Patients have been offered consultations over
62 mobile phones or videos, but also where relevant, equipped with innovative telehealth
63 and telecare products in the form of a personal digital assistant. Mobile communication
64 devices used as medical devices have an extremely useful way of communication and
65 exchange of the information between patients and healthcare providers, including
66 hospitals, supporting some aspects of clinical diagnosis and education. The benefits
67 of mobile devices are boundless, but there is a growing concern around the potential
68 contamination of their surfaces [1,2]. The transmission of microbial infections during
69 epidemics and pandemics through surface contamination became a public awareness
70 from the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic, and uncovered the relevance of the
71 disinfection practices that can be available to everyone [3], as the pathogens colonize
72 the surfaces and in consequence lead to increased transmission of infections. The
73 cleaning regime is relevant for all medical devices, as the microorganisms attach to a
74 surface, produce extracellular polymers, which promote further attachment and in
75 consequence formation of clinically relevant biofilm. The presence of biofilm
76 contributes to a decreased susceptibility of the microorganism to disinfectants, and
77 therefore creating a significant bioburden for public health.

78 The most common way of removing pathogens from the medical surfaces of is
79 sterilization through steam or radiation or chemical treatment. These procedures are
80 usually not suitable for the devices that have electronic components, but also, they are
81 not widely available to the society. In example, people who live with diabetes require
82 frequent control of the sugar levels, which are usually provided by inexpensive

83 glucometers in long-term care facilities. There is a wide range of glucometers used at
84 the various facilities and each has its own cleaning requirements per the manufacturer
85 [4]. In cases where the manufacturer does not provide any cleaning recommendations,
86 use of e.g. an EPA-registered high-level disinfectant is the standard [5]. However,
87 inappropriate disinfection may lead to increase of the microorganisms' transmission
88 and in consequence infection rate within the facility. To reduce bacterial contamination
89 risks time intervals between decontamination must be identified and regular
90 decontamination of mobile communication devices must be performed, along with
91 ensuring proper patient education on hand hygiene [6].

92 The meta-analysis on the dissemination of pathogens and studies to identify effective
93 prevention measures was already reported [7]. It was found that only 8% of healthcare
94 workers routinely cleaned their mobile communication devices resulting in a rate of
95 contamination between 40% and 100%. Coagulase-negative Staphylococci and
96 *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) were the most common bacteria with 10 up to
97 95.3% proportion of them were Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA). Another review
98 reported microbial presence on mobile phones in both health care and community
99 settings [8]. A total of 56 studies from 24 countries were included in the review. In 54
100 out of 56 sources the presence of bacteria was confirmed along 16 studies also
101 reported presence of fungi. *S. aureus* and coagulase-negative Staphylococci were the
102 most frequent organisms identified on mobile phones. These two species along with
103 *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) were present in over a third of studies both in health care and
104 community samples. MRSA, *Acinetobacter* sp., and *Bacillus* sp. were present in over
105 a third of the studies in health care settings only. The *E. coli* (and *Streptococci* sp) are
106 the first bacteria to colonize the gastrointestinal tract of humans upon birth, paving the
107 way for the establishment of species of the *Bifidobacterium*, *Bacteroides* and other
108 genera [9].

109 Application of mobile devices in healthcare is becoming an integral part of modern
110 medicine, with a potential global public health risk for microbial transmission. The aim
111 of the presented studies was to perform a multi-mode examination on the potential
112 role of glass display as well as a metallic cover of the mobile communication devices
113 in the occurrence of bacterial biofilms formed by *E. coli*. The specific purpose was to
114 indicate how long it will take for bacteria to colonize relatively smooth surfaces and to

115 easily detect the colonization. The *E. coli* was selected as a well-established model
116 organism for the study of surface bacterial colonization.

117 The *E. coli* colonization was carried out on stainless steel and glass surfaces, as
118 these two materials are commonly used in mobile devices, with longer life-span
119 comparing to plastic surfaces. The innovative approach to bacteria and biofilm
120 detection was applied, where multimodal measurement techniques such as Kelvin
121 probe, infrared spectroscopy, and digital holographic tomography.

122 Kelvin probe is a non-contact, capacitively coupled voltage measuring technique
123 capable of sensing low (typically up to a few volts) potential differences between the
124 probe conductive tip and the analyzed material surface directly beneath the probe. It
125 is referred to as a Contact Potential Difference (CPD) or Surface Potential (SP). CPD
126 results from a dissimilarity in the Work Function (WF) of the probe tip metal and the
127 examined material and it is thus very sensitive to any surface contamination or
128 changes in its chemical composition. The method was originally established by lord
129 Kelvin [10], technologically advanced by Zisman to use ac modulation technique [11]
130 and recently adopted by Baikie to use off-null detection method in Scanning Kelvin
131 Probe (SKP) [12] providing linear profiles and 2D maps of the CPD and WF distribution
132 in large (tens of mm) regions [13]. Although theoretical foundations of using off-null
133 detection SKP in biological tissue analysis have been laid down [14], no literature
134 evidence has been found so far for its use to study attachment of bacteria and biofilm
135 growth in large specimen surface regions. Kelvin probe attachment is also commonly
136 used in Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) developing Kelvin Probe Force Microscopy
137 (KPFM) known also as Scanning Surface Potential Microscopy (SSPM). Although it is
138 a truly valuable research tool of nanometer three-dimensional resolution, it offers very
139 narrow spatial region to be explored (tens of μm) and moreover, it is still discussable
140 whether it can provide a true contact potential difference (and thus WF) not obscured
141 by the atomic-scale tip-object distance and the resulting local distortion of the energy
142 bands altering WF values [15]. Yet, KPFM has been successively applied to map the
143 micro-scale distribution and provide insight into the attachment process of *P.*
144 *aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* on Au and stainless steel surfaces [16], adhesion of single
145 *B. thuringiensis* and *B. anthracis* spores to solid Au, Si and mica surfaces [17] or
146 microscale inhibition of bacterial adhesion and further biofilm formation on polymeric

147 surfaces covered with antimicrobial bromohexane N-alkylated polyethyleneimine
148 brushes [18], just to name a few its bacteria-related scientific applications.

149 Fourier transform infrared microscopy (μ FTIR) was used to confirm the
150 presence of biofilm formation on the stainless-steel surfaces. This vibrational
151 spectroscopic technique is a powerful tool for bacterial analysis, enabling direct
152 detection, identification and classification of microorganisms [19–21]. Moreover, it is
153 widely used to study the biochemical composition of biofilm produced by various
154 bacteria [22,23]. μ FTIR allows the investigation of the spatial distribution of proteins,
155 lipids and polysaccharides, providing a two dimensional map of the absorption as a
156 function of wavenumber throughout the sample surface. The appearance of bacterial
157 typical signals, such as strong absorbance in the nucleic acid and polysaccharide
158 region ($1200\text{-}900\text{ cm}^{-1}$) [24], is a strong evidence of the existence of *E. coli* cells on
159 the studied surface. μ FTIR has been also demonstrated as bacterial viability
160 assessment method [25], allowing discrimination between living and death cells.

161 The evaluation and confirmation of the bacterial biofilm and formation on the glass
162 surface the digital holographic tomography (DHT), which is suitable for non-contact
163 and non-destructive 3D optical imaging of single cells, was applied. In DHT based on
164 the limited-angle holographic tomography [26–28], the series of digital holograms is
165 registered at various incident angles of the illumination beam. Based on the principles
166 of optical diffraction tomography, it is possible to reconstruct 3D refractive index (RI)
167 tomograms of optically transparent objects by interferometric, tomographic (at various
168 illumination angles) imaging [29,30]. The provided RI-data are directly related with the
169 local changes of the intracellular density, particularly protein density, what can be used
170 for quantitative phenotyping of living, unlabeled cells. DHT is label-free, non-invasive,
171 fast and high-resolution technique being an alternative to the microscopic techniques:
172 scanning confocal fluorescence microscopy or 2D imaging techniques as fluorescence
173 microscopy, or phase contrast and differential interference contrast microscopy,
174 commonly used in biology and biomedical applications. Recently, there have been
175 many reports on the application potential of this technique, including for example
176 studies on: hematology [31], oncology [32], cell biology [33,34], neuroscience [35],
177 drug discovery [36], microbiology etc.

178 2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

179 2.1. Substrates

180 A medical- and food-grade stainless steel (grade 316L, UNS S31603) was selected
181 as a model metallic substrate. Round specimens (16 mm in diameter) machined
182 directly of a 0,5 mm thick flat sheet metal were grinded using super fine (2500 grit)
183 sandpaper to obtain average roughness $R_z=1.25 \mu\text{m} \pm 0.98 \mu\text{m}$ (verified using
184 roughness tester Mitutoyo SurfTest SJ-210). The specimens were then ultrasonically
185 cleaned in distilled water, acetone, absolute ethanol (both analytical grade) and
186 distilled water again (15 min in each bath), naturally dried and stored in clean
187 laboratory air to naturally re-passivate their surface. One half of the specimen surface
188 was subsequently masked with pressure-sensitive polysiloxane self-adhesive
189 polyimide film (70110, PPI Adhesive Products Ltd.) as illustrated in Figure 1.

190 To examine the biofilm formation on glass surfaces the glass-bottom micro-dishes (μ -
191 Dish 35 mm low, Ibidi, Germany; average glass surface roughness $R_z=0.094 \mu\text{m} \pm$
192 $0.019 \mu\text{m}$) were used. In order to avoid external bacterial contamination, all stainless
193 steel specimens masked with 70110 tape as well as glass micro-dishes were sterilized
194 in an autoclave at 121°C for 20 minutes prior to biofilm culture.

195

196 **Figure 1.** Stainless steel specimen masked with 70110 tape (with schematically
197 outlined path along which the Kelvin probe was relocated in line scan).

198 2.2. *Bacterial suspension*

199 A reference strain of *Escherichia coli* (E.coli) ATCC® 2592 bacteria (BioMaxima)
200 was used for this study. A bacterial suspension was prepared from a 24 hours culture
201 at a density of 0.5 McFarland (1.5×10^8 CFU/ml) (BioMaxima). Each stainless steel and
202 glass-surface specimen was placed in a sterile flask in 100 ml of nutrient agar (BTL)
203 inoculated with 1ml of standard strain. The whole was kept under continuous stirring
204 on a shaker (Elpin, 180 rpm) at 37°C. Biofilm-covered steel and glass-surface
205 specimens were disassembled after 24 and 72 hours respectively and excess medium
206 was washed off with sterile distilled water (5ml). Each specimen was then
207 resuspended in 100 µl of sterile water and stored in a refrigerator (4°C) for further
208 analysis, which was carried out generally in 1-3 hours. Reference stainless steel
209 specimens were prepared in an analogous way however, in this case the nutrient agar
210 was not inoculated with bacterial suspension. The 5 specimens of biofilm as well as 5
211 reference specimens were prepared for each incubation time duration.

212 2.3. *SEM topography analysis*

213 The 316L stainless steel specimens bred for 24 hours in bacteria-agar suspension
214 were also prepared for SEM analysis; in this case they were passively desiccator-dried
215 for 7 days and analyzed without any additional metallization. Surface microtopography
216 analysis was performed using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) (Ga-FIB Helios
217 NanoLab™ 600i, FEI) fitted with EDT detector and operated at low 2.0 kV accelerating
218 voltage (corresponding to 0.17 nA electron beam current) in order not to destroy
219 bacterial substance. Basic SEM image analysis was performed using ImageJ software
220 (ver. 1.53e) package and its image binarization and particle analysis macros.

221 2.4. *Scanning Kelvin probe*

222 An environmental Scanning Kelvin probe (SKP) with off-null detection system
223 (SKP5050, KP Technology, Scotland) was used for all CPD measurements. The probe
224 oscillator was supplied at 40 a.u. and 67.0 Hz, the probe backing voltage V_b (routed to
225 the probe tip) was varied between +/- 5.0 V, 4×10^7 V/A current gain and tenfold signal
226 averaging was applied while the gradient was maintained at 200 a.u. by the off-null
227 system detection algorithm. A stainless-steel probe tip (supplied by the SKP

228 manufacturer) with a diameter of 1 mm was used. The probe tip was cleaned with
229 absolute ethyl alcohol and air-dried before operation. Stainless steel specimens
230 encrusted with *E. coli* biofilm were rinsed by dipping them in distilled water and gently
231 air-dried. The masking tape was then unpeeled, and the samples were fixed on a
232 mobile SKP apparatus stage. CPD measurements were performed under laboratory
233 conditions (temperature 21-24°C, humidity 30-40% RH) as 10 mm long line scans as
234 well as 10x10 mm 2D scans (with 0.5 mm increments) traversing the center of the
235 specimen. CPD measurement conditions allow to estimate the effective area observed
236 by the Kelvin probe as ca. 1 mm². Therefore, CPD determined at a single point along
237 a scanline (and in 2D maps) corresponded to the average value over the area of 1 mm²
238 under the probe tip. The calibration step was performed using Au-evaporated
239 reference specimen to calculate WF of the probe tip material WF_{tip} .

240 The recorded data was averaged and statistically analyzed (using Shapiro-Wilk and
241 Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test as well as 1 way ANOVA) at 95 % confidence
242 interval.

243 2.5. μ FTIR evaluation

244 Nicolet iN10 MX FTIR microscope (Thermo Scientific Inc., USA) equipped with a
245 liquid nitrogen cooled MCT-A detector and a germanium Slide-On Ge Micro-Tip ATR
246 accessory was used to spatially map out the surface constituents of the analyzed
247 stainless steel specimen with bacterial film as well as the reference bacteria-free
248 specimen region (i.e. masked with polyimide film during bacteria culture). The FTIR
249 microscope was continuously purged with dry air. The 10x10 maps were collected with
250 the rectangular aperture array of 50×50 μm^2 with spatial resolution of 50 μm (thus,
251 0.5 x 0.5 mm area of the specimen was scanned). Each spectrum was recorded in the
252 range of 4000–650 cm^{-1} at a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and with 128 or 512
253 accumulated scans for samples and the background, respectively.

254 Data analysis was carried out using the Omnic and Omnic Picta software (Thermo
255 Scientific Inc., USA) and OriginPro 2019 program (OriginLab Corporation, USA). The
256 spectra preprocessing included: baseline corrections and smoothing with the Savitzky-
257 Golay filter (parameters: polynomial order 2, window 35 [37]).

258 2.6. Digital holographic tomographic examination

259 The commercial off-axis Mach–Zehnder interferometric setup with a rotatable
260 scanning mirror (3D Cell Explorer, Nanolive, Switzerland) was used. The series of
261 digital holograms were registered at the 520 nm wavelength by dry microscope
262 objective (60×, numerical aperture NA=0.8, Nikon) for each position of the scanning
263 mirrors on rotatable arm of interferometer. The reconstruction of digital holograms, 3D-
264 RI tomograms and rendered 3D visualizations of bacteria cells were performed by
265 STEVE software (Nanolive, Switzerland). Each 3D-RI tomogram contains 95 slices
266 (2D-RI tomograms). The digital staining of the single bacteria cells was performed
267 based on the reconstructed 3D-RI distribution, which enables the visualization of the
268 single bacteria cells present in the examined sample by determining the range of RI-
269 values corresponding to the volume of the bacteria cells.

270 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

271 3.1 SEM imaging of *E. coli*-encrusted 316L steel surface

272 Figure 2 A shows an exemplary low-magnification (x100) surface topography of
273 316L stainless steel specimen bred for 24 hours in *E. coli* bacterial suspension. Even
274 though the breed time was relatively short the specimen surface has become
275 irregularly encrusted with bacterial colonies at average surface coverage factor 0.6 %,
276 median surface area 48 μm^2 . They colonies were localized mainly in surface crevices
277 or near other steel face defects or irregularities as it is evidenced in Figure 2 B. This
278 can be related to the increased surface roughness within these areas, which could
279 have influenced ability of the bacteria to attach to the surface [38]. Dehydrated bacteria
280 displayed a regular rod-like shape with 1.6 μm length and 0.4 μm width on average.
281 The mean dimensions recorded for the air-dried *E. coli* cells compare well with those
282 reported in the literature [39].

283

284 **Figure 2.** Surface topography of 316L stainless steel specimen bred for 24h in
 285 bacterial suspension: (A) 2 x 1.4 mm surface region, (B) *E. coli* biofilm structure
 286 (original SEM images, unprocessed).

287 3.2 CPD scans

288 In order to calculate WF of the probe tip material WF_{tip} a calibration was performed
 289 using Au-evaporated reference specimen, as shown in Figure 3 A. The mean value of
 290 the CPD recorded between the probe tip and Au reference surface amounted to
 291 $+0.378 \pm 0.032$ V. Therefore, as the work function of gold WF_{Au} may be assumed to
 292 vary between 5.16 eV and 5.33 eV [12] thus WF_{tip} remains within 4.78-4.95 eV range
 293 which perfectly agrees with values 4.76-4.96 eV provided in literature for
 294 polycrystalline 316L stainless steel [13]. Thus, the mean value of the $WF_{tip}=4.87$ eV
 295 was adopted for further CPD measurement data processing as the 1 mm in diameter
 296 SKP probe tip inherently averages crystal grain-related local WF variations. CPD
 297 spatial distribution of exemplary tape-masked 316L stainless steel specimen dipped
 298 for 24h in distilled water was shown in Figure 3 B. Statistical analysis of such
 299 specimens revealed the mean CPD= $+143$ mV for 24h H₂O-dipped 316L steel material,
 300 (corresponding to the mean WF = 5.01 eV) while for specimens immersed for 72h the
 301 mean CPD = $+130$ mV (corresponding to WF = 4.91 eV). Both CPD values were
 302 statistically different (as evaluated using ANOVA 1 way test) thus the 72h-long water
 303 dipping of 316L stainless resulted in statistically meaningful change of its WF although
 304 the dissimilarity of the WF registered in this period was equal to 0.1 eV i.e. it was
 305 smaller than 2% of its initial value. This minor change in WF was related to slow

306 electrochemical-in-origin oxidation of the 316L steel surface by H₂O and the resulting
307 emergence of Fe and Cr oxide and peroxide precipitates which formed a moderately-
308 conducting barrier film passivating the steel surface [40].

309

310 **Figure 3.** Exemplary CPD distribution: (A) along Au reference surface, (B) for tape-
311 masked 316L stainless steel specimen dipped in distilled water for 24 hours.

312 The analysis performed for the tape-masked fragments of the 316L steel specimens
313 showed that 24 hours-long contact with the masking tape resulted in the mean
314 CPD=+360 mV while 72 hours-long period increased its CPD to +399mV. Those two
315 CPD values were statistically different thus the contact with the polysiloxane adhesive
316 of the masking tape changed the CPD of the 316L steel and the prolonged 72 hours-
317 long exposure was shifting CPD towards higher values (although an exact
318 dependency of the CPD shift with time was not evaluated as it was not within the scope
319 of the current study). Thus, it suggests that some remains of the polysiloxane adhesive
320 were present on the steel surface after peeling the tape off, as it has been discussed
321 further in the manuscript section related to μ FTIR analysis. Moreover, the analysis
322 indicates that the CPD of the 316L specimen part screened out with the siloxane
323 adhesive tape is not suitable as an invariable reference value.

324 Fig. 4 illustrates exemplary CPD variations in 316L stainless steel specimen half-
325 masked with 70110 tape and encrusted with *E.coli* bred for 24 and 72 hours
326 respectively. The mean CPD (averaged among all examined specimens) in the part
327 encrusted with *E. coli* bred for 24h and 72h yields +57 mV and +7 mV respectively and

328 were statistically different. On the other hand, the mean CPD of the reference 316L
329 steel specimens retained in bacteria-free agar for 24h and 72h yielded -56 mV and -
330 15 mV respectively.

331

332 **Figure 4.** Exemplary CPD distribution in 316L stainless steel specimen half-masked
333 with PPI tape and encrusted with *E. coli* cultivated for: (A) 24h, (B) 72h.

334

335 Thus, not only the mean CPD values of the bacterial films bred for 24h and 72h were
336 statistically different from each other but they were also statistically different from the
337 corresponding reference specimens produced in bacteria-free agar. The mean CPD
338 of the specimens covered with bacterial film were also statistically different from the
339 mean CPD values recorded for specimens dipped in distilled water.

340 The above findings were graphically summarized in the box chart shown in Figure 5,
341 which was additionally scaled with WF values for comparison purposes. While the
342 mean CPD of the 316L specimens kept in bacteria-free agar was rising with the
343 retention time, the mean CPD of the bred-time corresponding bacterial films was
344 declining as the biofilm breed time was prolonged. Thus, the presence of the bacterial
345 colonies on the 316L steel specimen surface not only charged its CPD but also
346 significantly altered its time evolution.

347

348 **Figure 5.** Statistical CPD variations in 316L stainless steel (SS) specimens
 349 undergoing different treatments, where 24h and 72h indicate treatment duration,
 350 SS_{H2O} denotes water dipping, SS_{PPI} symbolizes tape-masking, SS_{AGAR} indicates
 351 reference specimens prepared using bacteria-free agar while SS_{E.COLI} refers to
 352 bacterial biofilm).

353 The observed decrease in CPD of *E.coli* biofilm on 316L stainless steel along with the
 354 increase in incubation time can be explained as follows. Most bacteria (including
 355 *E. coli*) above their the whole-cell isoelectric point (IEP, which for most bacteria lays
 356 in the low pH range of 1.5-4.5), show a negative net charge, which in turn is related to
 357 the number of charged acidic and basic groups present in bacterial surface polymers
 358 and in their extracellular polymeric substances matrix [41]. Thus, as the number of
 359 *E.coli* bacteria and their colonies increased along with the biofilm incubation time the
 360 net negative charge of the biofilm also increased. In result, the CPD was shifted
 361 towards more negative values as the Kelvin probe reacts not only to variations in WF
 362 but it also identifies the charged state of the analyzed surface. Thus, the observed
 363 CPD decrease was more likely to be related to the change in the surface charge
 364 density (linked to the increasing number of bacteria on the examined surface) than to
 365 a change in the WF of the bacterial biofilm as a whole.

366 Moreover, even a low number of *E.coli* bacterial clusters (corresponding to ca. 0.6%
367 of the specimen surface, as verified using SEM) formed during the initial 24-long breed
368 period was detected by SKP. The additional benefit of using SKP method to detect
369 and monitor bacterial *E. coli* biofilm development is related to its large (hundreds of
370 mm²) surface area analysis capabilities as compared to KPFM (offering μm-sized
371 spans) and thus it may be applicable in scientific examinations of bacterial incursions
372 in real objects like medical, personal care or amusement devices.

373 3.2 μFTIR

374 ATR-FTIR mapping has been used for chemical identification and distribution
375 of materials on the steel substrates. One of the key advantages of ATR-FTIR
376 spectroscopy is the ability to measure even very thin films in a relatively undisturbed
377 way without the need of any specific sample preparation, which makes it a versatile
378 tool for investigating biofilm development in situ [42]. Representative images of
379 reference stainless steel and *E. coli* biofilm-covered specimens are presented in
380 Figure 6. These maps clearly show that the reference area is free of organic matter,
381 while bacteria cells are present in the biofilm specimen region. It could be concluded
382 from the integrated intensity of the absorption band between 3050-2900 cm⁻¹ assigned
383 to vibrations of CH₂ and CH₃ groups, which is substantially higher for bacteria spectra.
384 In accordance with the obtained spectral maps (Figure 6 B-D), the distribution of
385 bacteria single-cells is not uniform and cells clusters are present.

386

387 **Figure 6.** Representative ATR-FTIR mappings. **Upper:** The distribution of organic
 388 matter in analyzed areas by integrating the CH₂ stretching band at 2920 cm⁻¹ in the
 389 ATR-FTIR spectrum (3000-2800 cm⁻¹): (A) - reference stainless steel specimen, (B) -
 390 E. coli biofilm-covered specimen. **Bottom:** The distribution of proteins from integration
 391 of Amide I band area (1700-1600 cm⁻¹) (C) and lipids based on integration of the
 392 carbonyl band $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ at 1735 cm⁻¹ (D) in bacteria specimen area. **White scale**
 393 **bar:** 50 μm .

394

395 The average spectrum shown in Figure 7. identifies the presence of inorganic
 396 impurities (corundum and silica carbide) on the stainless-steel surface in bacteria-free

397 specimen region. A very weak band at around 1260 cm^{-1} corresponds to $-\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)$ and
 398 a weak broad band at 1100 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $-\text{Si}-\text{O}-\text{Si}-$ and $\text{Al}-\text{O}-\text{Si}$
 399 groups [43], which leads to a conclusion that these are sandpaper and siloxane
 400 adhesive residues.

401
 402 **Figure 7.** Average ATR-FTIR spectra of analyzed areas (blue line: bacteria-free
 403 specimen region, red line: *E. coli* biofilm-covered specimen region).

404 In turn, the average spectrum obtained for the steel surface covered with bacteria,
 405 shown in Figure 7 is typical for *Escherichia coli* strains [44,45] and it is dominated by
 406 the absorption of proteins and lipid membrane constituents [22,46,47]. The most
 407 intensive is Amide I band at 1640 cm^{-1} , which is mainly corresponding to the stretching
 408 vibration $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ carbonyl groups of the peptide bond. In addition, in bacteria infrared
 409 spectra in the wavenumber range of $1300\text{-}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ nucleic acids bands are
 410 observed, on the other hand, in the $1200\text{-}950\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region an absorption from
 411 carbohydrates occurs. The complex band at 1074 cm^{-1} can be mainly assigned to the
 412 C-O-C glycosidic linkage and C-O-C stretching of carbohydrates in bacterial cell walls,
 413 as well as to the stretching vibrations of PO_2^- groups in phospholipids and nucleic
 414 acids. The weak shoulder band at $\sim 1745\text{ cm}^{-1}$ originates from stretching vibrations of
 415 ester carbonyl groups ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) is related to lipoproteins and phospholipids. This band is

416 considered to be a marker of EPS (extracellular polymeric substances) [46,48]. The
417 presence of the intensive and broad band at 3400 cm^{-1} mostly arising from stretching
418 vibrations of OH groups in water molecules is the proof that the bacteria cells
419 contained in the analyzed biofilm stayed in hydrated, probably viable form.

420 3.3 DHT examination

421 The DHT was used for detection of the formation of bacterial biofilm on the
422 glass-surface without the presence of any nutrients by reconstructed 3D-RI
423 distributions. The average length and width of the adult (non-dividing) *E. coli* cells on
424 glass-surface was equal to $2.8\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and $1.2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$, respectively. Obtained results
425 indicated that the *E. coli* cells cultivated on this surface have larger spatial size than
426 cells cultivated on steel-surface during the SEM examination, what may be related
427 with the cells' dehydration process necessary for SEM imaging.

428 However, during the cell division, the bacteria cell is changing its morphology
429 and RI-values. Generally, cell division (or cytokinesis) is one of the fundamental
430 processes enabling the proliferation of both prokaryotic and eukaryotic cells.
431 Cytokinesis is induced by a complex of proteins that constitute the division apparatus
432 [49]. This process is spatially and temporarily correlated with other cell processes as:
433 DNA replication (duplication of the genetic material), segregation of nucleoids and
434 cytoplasm (their distribution between two cells), generation of the septum between two
435 cells and the final separation of cells' walls and membranes. The RI value of cell
436 cytoplasm is linearly related to its protein concentration, local protein concentration of
437 a cell [50] associated with the DNA replication and the segregation of the nucleoids
438 can be retrieved from RI-data. Moreover, the initial (parent) cell prepares for division
439 by enlarging the cell wall, cell membrane and overall volume, what leads to the
440 changes of the cell morphology which can be also retrieved from reconstructed RI-
441 data. Therefore, it was necessary to analyze the variation of RI-values during this
442 physiological process to include in our examination also such kinds of cells.
443 Representative and exemplary results related with cell division are shown on Figure 8.
444 Initially, the bacteria cell has uniform distribution of the cytoplasm inside the cell
445 (Figure 8A) and the local maxima of RI-values representing the local increase of the
446 protein's concentration related with the location of the nucleoids and ribosomes are
447 present. When the cells division is beginning the *E. coli* cell's size is increased.

448 Moreover, the local concentration of the proteins inside the cell can be observed (see
449 Figure 8 B).

450

451 **Figure 8.** The representative 2D-RI tomograms of the initial *E. coli* single-cell before
452 cell division (A), after DNA replication and segregation of nucleoids (B) and during
453 septum synthesis (C).

454 It is related with the local increase of the RI-values at the opposite ends of cell revealed
455 segregation of the nucleoids and cytoplasm following the DNA replication. The
456 synthesis of the septum in the cell center is indicated by the decrease of the cell
457 diameter in the central region (see Figure 8 C).

458 Based on the representative 2D-RI tomograms, the range of RI-values' variation
459 between the dividing cells and already divided cells was determined to visualize all
460 cells present on the examined glass-surface. It was shown that the range of RI-values'
461 variation between analyzed cells is from 1.345 to 1.380 (see Figure 8). Obtained
462 results are indicating that the spatial distribution of the RI-values is depending on the
463 stage of the bacteria cells division and it is possible to characterize this process based
464 on measured 2D/3D-RI tomograms. Furthermore, the existence of such variations of
465 the RI-distribution indicates that the *E. coli* cells on the glass-surface without presence
466 of any nutrients have the ability for cell division and multiplication. However, it should
467 be pointed out that the RI-values and 2D-RI distribution is depending also on the kind
468 of the surrounding medium and its RI-value [51] , therefore depending on the used
469 procedures of sample's preparation, the determined RI-data can be different.

470 After determination of this RI-values' range inside the single cell, the digital
471 staining was performed to visualize all bacteria cells on the glass-surface. The
472 exemplary results are shown on Figure 9.

473

474 **Figure 9.** The representative results of the 2D-RI tomograms (A), reconstructed,
 475 rendered and digitally stained 3D-RI tomograms of *E. coli* cells (B) indicating the initial
 476 sample and the process of biofilm formation after 24 and 72 hours of cultivation.

477

478 It can be seen that after 24 hours the *E. coli* bacteria are able to biofilm formation on
 479 the glass-surface without the presence of nutrients as in case of the steel-surface.
 480 Moreover, the number of cells is still increased over time, which indicates that despite

481 the lack of nutrients in the surrounding medium the living bacteria cells can still be able
482 to divide on glass-surface. Moreover, the rendered 3D-RI tomograms demonstrated
483 that on the analyzed surface the bacteria cells are forming the monolayer (see movie1
484 in Supplementary Materials).

485 3.4 The assessment of obtained results of multi-modal measurements

486 The food- and medical-grade 316L austenitic stainless steel was used in our biofilm-
487 adhesion experiments as a substrate for Kelvin probe CPD examination while
488 borosilicate glass was applied in DHT imaging. Both substrates have their unique but
489 different properties (high electrical conductance versus strong dielectric character as
490 well as differences in roughness and thus bacterial film affinity) and they represent
491 medically relevant surfaces and standard engineering materials used in common
492 products. Yet, both types of tested materials (glass and metal) as hydrophilic are less
493 likely to be colonized by *E. coli* than e.g. plastics or other hydrophobic and non-polar
494 surfaces, according to Beloin [52] and Donlan [53]. All experiments were also
495 performed in temperature and humidity conditions closely approximating typical room
496 conditions, thus bacterial growth was observed in every-day circumstances faced by
497 medical and entertaining devices handled by humane users.

498 In all experiments, a scanning Kelvin probe with off-null detection was used to
499 identify intact *E. coli* biofilms over a large area (50 mm²) of the metallic samples. The
500 relative standard error of the CPD values recorded for water-dipped 316L stainless
501 steel substrates was below 0.7% and it was higher than the data variation (0.3%)
502 recorded for Au reference used as the WF calibration surface however, such variation
503 in CPD in real polycrystalline metallic surfaces are commonly observed. On the other
504 hand, the relative standard error of the CPD measured for biofilm-covered 316L steel
505 specimens was dependent on the biofilm cultivation time; while for 24 hours it was not
506 higher than 2.0% yet for 72 hours-long cultivation, it was generally below 10% but a
507 specimen with over 50% relative standard error was also discovered. This may
508 indicate that the higher variation in CPD measurements observed in biofilms is related
509 to the biofilm itself (its arbitrary geometry and random distribution of single cells and
510 cells clusters) rather than to the Kelvin probe instrument. The *E. coli* cells and formed
511 biofilms can exhibit the spatial heterogeneity related to the different locations of single-

512 cells attachment to the surface and different process of the biofilm development, what
513 may be responsible for higher statistical spread of the measurement results.

514 As summarized in Figure 4, *E. coli* biofilm cultivated for 24 hours has a substantially
515 higher CPD value than that recorded for a biofilm cultivated for 72 hours. This is related
516 to the bacterial film development, proliferation, and the corresponding increase in
517 number of bacteria cells per surface unit, as illustrated on glass specimens by
518 holotomographic imaging presented in Figure 9. As the goal of the presented research
519 was to detect formation of living *E. coli* biofilms, the cells could not be dehydrated
520 (dried) before holotomographic imaging and CPD scans thus, water adsorbed within
521 the biofilms may interfere with the obtained results. This effect was observed in case
522 of the SEM results, where the cells' dehydration led to the decrease of their size in
523 comparison with the results of the DHT examination. The biofilm samples on glass and
524 stainless-steel surfaces were prepared with the same manner, therefore the possible
525 dehydration of bacteria cells has been excluded by the IR microscopy which confirmed
526 the hydrated form of cells on stainless steel surface by the presence of the intensive
527 and broad band at 3400 cm^{-1} mostly arising from stretching vibrations of OH groups in
528 water molecules.

529 Our holotomographic observations (Fig.9) suggest that the *E. coli* cells are dividing
530 and multiplexing easily and form a bacterial monolayer on glass surface. Another
531 possible cause of the observed variations in CPD may be related to the changes of
532 the bacteria cell size or their spatial reorientation during the biofilm development in
533 time, when the concentration of bacteria cells in the biofilm and on the examined
534 surfaces was increased. This was partially confirmed by the DHT examination, which
535 demonstrated that during the cell division the individual parent cells exhibit the time-
536 resolved morphological changes (including cell's size) and local changes of the
537 protein's concentration related to the cytokinesis. Such process can be present also
538 during CPD scans, even if the used surfaces in each examination were differing not
539 only in its basic material composition but also in the roughness, which may modify the
540 biofilm growth and its morphology. On the other hand, studies performed by Rodriguez
541 suggests that the surface roughness is not significantly correlated with the
542 *L. monocytogenes* attachment and biofilm formation on stainless steel [54] and similar
543 observations not linking the biofilm growth rate with surface roughness were also
544 reported by Percival for 316-grade stainless steel and bacterial flora commonly found

545 in potable water (including *Acinetobacter sp*, *Pseudomonas spp*, *Methylobacterium*
546 *sp*, and *Corynebacterium / Arthrobacter spp*) [55].

547 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

548 In summary, we have presented a novel multimode approach to a non-contact and
549 label-free detection of the *E. coli* biofilm formation on the glass and stainless-steel
550 surfaces. It was demonstrated that the synergistic analysis using selected techniques
551 enables the multi-parametric characterization of bacterial biofilm formation on optically
552 transparent and non-transparent as well as conductive and non-conductive surfaces.
553 The here-proposed approach combines the chemical composition of bacterial biofilms
554 with their electrical, optical, morphological properties. The method enables
555 examination of the samples on larger scale, and can be easily adapted by conventional
556 microbiological laboratories, where such samples are investigated on daily basis.

557 To analyze the non-transparent and conductive or semi-conductive samples as
558 stainless steel, the KP, SEM and IR-microscopy was applied, and cross-examined
559 using classical SEM microscopy. According to our knowledge this is the first attempt
560 to examine biofilm formation by measuring the contact potential difference CPD
561 distributions using scanning probe, as the available literature presents studies with
562 nanometer resolution on single-cell level by means of KPFM. We investigated the CPD
563 of *E. coli* bacterial biofilms deposited on food- and medical- 316L-grade stainless steel
564 substrates under laboratory conditions closely mimicking those observed in everyday
565 practice. The CPD of the metallic 316L stainless steel substrate covered with juvenile
566 (24h old) *E. coli* biofilm changed significantly not only in comparison with the CPD of
567 the stainless steel itself, but it was also experimentally proven that it increased over
568 time as the biofilm was formed. This non-contact measurement technique can be used
569 to develop and verify tests of the bacterial biofilm existence on common solid surfaces
570 like stainless steel. The shape, dimensions, wettability, surface roughness, and CPD
571 are all expected to play a critical role in determining the adhesion force between a
572 bacterial biofilm and a planar substrate surface.

573 The IR-spectra confirmed that after 24 hours the biofilm formation on larger surfaces
574 can be detected based on the presence of the characteristic bands of: CH₂ and CH₃
575 groups, Amide I, nucleic acids, carbohydrates in bacterial cell walls, or lipoproteins

576 and phospholipids, considered to be a marker of extracellular polymeric substances
577 which are responsible for adhesion of biofilms to surfaces.

578 On the other hand, in case of the optically transparent, conductive/non-conductive
579 substrates, it was possible to use the DHT technique for analysis of the bacterial
580 biofilm formation. This approach based on the reconstructed RI-data, provided the
581 information about the local density and proteins changes inside the single-cells.
582 Obtained results have shown, that also in case of the glass surfaces the *E. coli* bacteria
583 are able to form a biofilm as observed for stainless steel. It was shown that the
584 dehydration of cells during SEM is significantly affecting the cells' morphology.
585 Moreover, it was demonstrated that this technique is suitable not only for visualization
586 of single-cells and biofilm formation, but also the cytokinesis process and during the
587 examination of the biofilm formation it is essential to take into consideration the fact,
588 that at the same time, bacteria cells forming the biofilm can be at different stages of
589 cell division and in consequence their morphology, proteins and cytoplasm
590 concentration will be changing.

591 The proposed techniques can be applied for the multi-parametric detection and
592 characterization of the biofilm formation and dynamics of this process on surfaces of
593 the most common materials (optically transparent/non-transparent, conductive/semi-
594 conductive or non-conductive) used in medical devices and instrumentation, but also
595 others used in everyday life as mobile phones. The accurate identification and
596 modeling of factors promoting bacterial cell adhesion and biofilm formation can prove
597 extremely important in controlling the consequences of intentional or accidental
598 bacterial surface contamination.

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